

Replication Package for -

Brooks, Ian & Whittard, Damian (2025) *Looking for Green ICT Jobs: The Pattern of Green ICT Employment in the United Kingdom*. ICT For Sustainability 2025

Table A1: List of variables used in the ASHE and ASHE-Census 2011 dataset

Variable	Categories	ASHE-Census
Basic hourly wage	Continuous variable calculated by the ratio of basic weekly earning to the total number of basic weekly paid hours	bpay/bhr
Female	Dummy variable	sex
Age Age-squared	Continuous variable with squared value	age age_squared
Ethnicity	Categorical variable (white; mixed/multiple ethnic groups; Asian/Asian British; Black/African/ Caribbean/ Black British; Other ethnic group)	aggethpuk11
Education	Categorical variable: Self-reported level of highest qualification. Grouped into five categories - no qualification, up to A-level, apprenticeship, Other/vocational qualification, degree or above)	hlqpuk11
Marital status	Dummy variable (1 for those married or in a registered same-sex civil partnership)	marstat
Born outside UK	Dummy variable	aggcobpuk113
Health – Fair to very bad	Dummy variable (0,1) for self-reported health created from a five-point scale of very good health, good health, fair health, bad health and very bad health	health
Dependent child	Categorical variable to indicate whether the individual is responsible for a dependent child – four categories include no dependent child in family; pre-school age (0-4); primary school (5-11) or senior school (12-18)	dpcefamuk11
Public transport user	Dummy variable whether individual is a public transport user	ptranspuk11
Disability	Dummy variable for those who report a disability that interferes with their day-to-day activity	disability

Experience Experience-squared	Continuous variable and squared term. Time in job calculated by year of observation, minus employment start year plus one	empstart_y
Part-time job	Dummy variable to indicate whether job is part-time	fulltime
Hourly paid	Dummy variable to indicate whether the individual was hourly paid	hourly_paid
Size of employer	Categorical variable for the employer size band. Four categories of 0-9, 10-49, 50 to 249 and 250 and over.	emp_size_band
Collective agreement	Dummy variable to indicate whether the individual is subject to a collective bargaining agreement	coll_agt
Foreign owned enterprise	Dummy variable to indicate whether the individual works for a foreign owned company	for_own
Sector	Categorical variable -11 industrial sectors	sector
Region	Categorical variable – government office region at workplace (NUTS1: North East, North West, Yorkshire, East Midlands, West Midlands, South West, East, London, South East, Wales)	region
Variable	Categories	Dependent Variables
Log of gross Hourly pay	Log of a variable calculated by the ratio of basic weekly earning to the total number of basic weekly paid hours (bpay/bhr)	Log_ghp
IT occupation and green industry IT occupation and sunset industry (Binary Variable)	Dummy variable to identify IT occupations and green/sunset industries. IT occupations identified using SOC codes (detailed in paper) green and sunset industries identified using SIC codes (detailed) in main paper.	it_occ_green_ind it_occ_brown_ind
IT industry green occupation	IT industries identified using SIC codes. Green occupation identified by matching UK occupations which match to one or more of the US green occupations identified via the O*NET project	It_ind_green_occ